

D6.3 Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Activities

Date: May 30, 2025

Document Identification			
Status	Final	Due Date	31/05/2025
Version	1.0	Submission Date	30/05/2025

Related WP	WP6	Document Reference	D6.3
Related Deliverable(s)	D6.1, D6.2	Dissemination Level (*)	PU
Lead Participant	FN	Lead Author	Pavlos Zafeiropoulos
Contributors	ALL	Reviewers	Piotr Dzierzak (PSNC)
			Gwennole Chappron (UNISTRA)

Keywords:
Dissemination, communication, branding, social media, clustering, outreach

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This document is issued within the frame and for the purpose of the HiDALGO2 project. Funded by the European Union. This work has received funding from the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) and Poland, Germany, Spain, Hungary, France, Greece under grant agreement number: 101093457. This publication expresses the opinions of the authors and not necessarily those of the EuroHPC JU and Associated Countries which are not responsible for any use of the information contained in this publication. **This deliverable is subject to final acceptance by the European Commission.** This document and its content are the property of the HiDALGO2 Consortium. The content of all or parts of this document can be used and distributed provided that the HiDALGO2 project and the document are properly referenced.

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Document information

List of Contributors	
Name	Partner
Pavlos Zafeiropoulos	FN
Kyriaki Daskaloudi	FN
Georgia Nikolakopoulou	FN
Lina Giannivasili	FN

Document history			
Version	Date	Change editors	Changes
0.1	07/04/2025	Pavlos Zafeiropoulos (FN)	First draft with TOC, bullets explaining content, responsibilities and timeline
0.2	07/04/2025	Marcin Lawenda (PSNC), Rahil Doshi (FAU)	ToC, timeline and responsibilities approved
0.3	06/05/2025	Pavlos Zafeiropoulos (FN)	First Draft
0.4	08/05/2025	Georgia Nikolakopoulou (FN)	Feedback on the content
0.5	12/05/2025	Pavlos Zafeiropoulos (FN)	Draft ready for internal Review
0.6	23/05/2025	Piotr Dzierzak (PSNC)	First reviewer comments
0.7	27/05/2025	Pavlos Zafeiropoulos (FN)	Reviewer comments resolved
0.8	28/05/2025	Gwennole Chappron (UNISTRA)	Second reviewer comments
0.9	29/05/2025	Pavlos Zafeiropoulos (FN)	Reviewer comments resolved
0.95	30/05/2025	Rahil Doshi	Quality assurance check
1.0	30/05/2025	Marcin Lawenda	Final check and improvements

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Quality control		
Role	Who (Partner short name)	Approval Date
Deliverable Leader	Pavlos Zafeiropoulos (FN)	27/05/2025
Quality Manager	Rahil Doshi (FAU)	30/05/2025
Project Coordinator	Marcin Lawenda (PSNC)	30/05/2025

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List of acronyms

Insert here all the acronyms appearing along the deliverable in alphabetical order.

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CIRCE	Computational Immediate Response Center for Emergencies
CoE	Centre of Excellence
Dx.y	Deliverable number y belonging to WP x
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud

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EuroHPC JU	EuroHPC Joint Undertaking
FN	Future Needs Management Consulting Ltd
HLRS	High-Performance Computing Center Stuttgart
HPC	High Performance Computing
HPDA	High Performance Data Analytics
ICCS - NTUA	Institute of Communications and Computer Systems of the National Technical University of Athens
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MTG	MeteoGrid
NUMPEX	Numérique pour Exascale (Digital for Exascale)
PSNC	Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center
PU	Public
SEAVEA	Software Environment for Actionable & VVUQ-evaluated Exascale Applications
SZE	Széchenyi István University
UNISTRA	University of Strasbourg
USTUTT	University of Stuttgart
WP	Work Package
WP6	Work Package 6

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Executive summary

This report, D6.3 “Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Activities,” provides a comprehensive overview of the outreach and engagement efforts undertaken by the HiDALGO2 project, focusing on the period from January 2024 (M13) up to and including April 2025 (M28). It reports on the implementation of the strategy laid out in D6.1 “Brand and Roadmap for Awareness Campaign” [1], and follows D6.2 “Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Activities,” [2] which reported on the period up to December 2023 (M12).

Assessing progress against relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), a view is provided of the progress achieved and contextualizes this with regard to the project and its aims as a whole. In broad terms, the relevant KPIs have been either met, or are on track to be met indicating the general success of the communication and dissemination activities to date. The report further highlights areas where particular focus will help ensure the project achieves maximal impact, given the expected needs and outputs over the period M29 - M48.

With regard to online communication channels, this report provides analysis of levels of traffic and engagement on different platforms and identifies relative strengths and weaknesses. These communication channels complement dissemination efforts such as the publication of papers and presentation of HiDALGO2 research and results at conferences and events.

Twelve peer-reviewed publications have been produced to date, with the project on track to meet the target of 25 by M48. These publications, along with popular articles and blog content, are promoted across project channels to maximise visibility. The project has also exceeded its KPI for participation in external events and has several ongoing collaborations with other groups and EU-funded projects. The HiDALGO2 project is thus well-positioned to maximise the impact of the outputs of its technical undertakings through the dissemination and communication of findings and applications being developed, reaching key audiences and stakeholders through a variety of pathways.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to present a comprehensive review of the communication and dissemination activities of the HiDALGO2 project. The communication and dissemination strategy implemented by the project is described in D6.1 “Brand and Roadmap for Awareness Campaign” [1] and D6.2 “Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Activities” [2], with the latter providing amendments to the original Roadmap described in D6.1.

This considers the period between the start of the HiDALGO2 project in January 2023 (M01) until the end of April 2025 (M28), with a particular focus on the period between January 2024 (M13) and April 2025 (M28), given that the communication and dissemination activities and relevant results for the preceding period were reported in D6.2.

Within the report, the relevant outputs and activities of the project are described and impacts reported against the KPIs laid out in the relevant Grant Agreement [3] (Project 101093457) and subsequently amended in Amendment No. AMD-101093457-3 [4].

1.2 Relation to other project work

The results of the dissemination, communication, and Clustering Activities, as part of Task 6.5 “Project Branding, Dissemination and Communication” are closely related to several other tasks and deliverables of the project, as described below:

WP5 “Tackling Global Challenges” (includes all the work related to the use cases): The results of this entire WP forms a significant part of the project’s dissemination given there is considerable interest by external stakeholders in how solutions and technical advances developed in the HiDALGO2 project can be applied to addressing Global Challenges, in particular related to greater risks created due to climate change.

- Task 6.2 “Project Exploitation and IPR Management”: This task will ensure the future exploitation and deployment of the project results by project partners and the continuation of the project research and innovation. Dissemination & Communication of all results is vital for this task.
- Task 6.3 “Expanding Competences by Trainings”: this aims to collect and share knowledge, best practices, available resources, applications and software frameworks for tackling the identified Global Challenges with HPC and AI. As such, activities under this task contribute considerably to the communication and dissemination of the project more broadly by helping audiences better understand HiDALGO2 applications. Further, outreach efforts work synergistically with this task by raising awareness of the training opportunities

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provided, and where possible, making recordings of training activities publicly available.

- Task 6.4 “Awareness Creation, Collaboration and Community Support”: This task aims to identify and engage a broader HiDALGO2 stakeholder community and national and international projects around the world that are related to HiDALGO2. Work under this task thus contributes significantly to the project’s communication goals by establishing links and connections that help amplify and disseminate HiDALGO2 communications and news.
- Deliverable D6.1 “Brand and Roadmap for Awareness Campaign” [1]: This provides the tools and guidelines to the HiDALGO2 consortium necessary for partners to contribute to the project’s communication and dissemination activities.
- Deliverable D6.2 “Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Activities (M12)” [2] reported on the first year of the implementation of the strategy laid out in D6.1, together with adjustments made to various aspects of the project’s communication and dissemination processes to improve performance and effectiveness.

Finally, WP6 aims to promote a sustainable operation of the Centre of Excellence, fostering communication and dissemination activities including training, workshops, collaboration with other projects and organisations and demonstrating the HiDALGO2 results to the general public.

1.3 Structure of the document

Following the introduction (**Chapter 1**), the document is structured in 5 additional chapters.

Chapter 2 presents a high-level view of the dissemination, communication & clustering activities undertaken by the HiDALGO2 project.

Chapter 3 provides a detailed description of the online communication conducted by the HiDALGO2 project on platforms managed by the project or its partners, including the project website, social media channels and newsletter.

Chapter 4 reports on the scientific publications produced by the project and articles published by third parties.

Chapter 5 covers the events such as conferences, workshops and training sessions at which the HiDALGO2 project has been presented, the collaborations in which the project has been engaged and the project’s planned clustering event.

Chapter 6 presents overarching conclusions drawing on the reporting from the preceding sections, describing key elements of the project’s dissemination and communication moving forward to ensure the success of these efforts.

The Annex presents supplementary tables and data.

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2 Dissemination, communication and clustering activities overview

Dissemination, communication and clustering activities are overlapping yet distinct elements of the HiDALGO2’s outreach strategy. This chapter provides an overview of the broad elements of this strategy and how they relate to the HiDALGO2 project’s research outputs and the activities of the project’s consortium partners.

2.1 Role of partners

As described in D6.1[1], from the outset of the project, all project partners have been involved in the communication and dissemination activities, with the contribution of each partner determined in part by the nature of their work and the results generated by the project.

For industrial partners, namely ATOS, MeteoGrid (MTG) and the High-Performance Computing Center Stuttgart (USTUTT), participation at, or hosting of events forms a key pathway through which they contribute to raising awareness about the project, its individual use cases and the technologies and applications being developed. These partners also draw on their extensive contacts with regulatory bodies and industry partners to broaden the HiDALGO2 community.

The academic partners, namely the Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC), the Centre for Modeling and Simulation in Strasbourg (UNISTRA), the Institute of Communications and Computer Systems of the National Technical University of Athens (ICCS) and the Széchenyi István University (SZE), play a more active role in the dissemination of project results to research institutes and universities through the publication and presentation of scientific papers, and participation in conferences and events aimed at academic audiences.

As Leader of Task 6.5 Project Branding, Dissemination and Communication, as well as Task 6.4 Awareness Creation, Collaboration and Community Support, consortium partner Future Needs (FN) plays a central role in coordinating all relevant activities of the other partners and implementing the strategy laid out in D6.1. This includes managing the communication channels of the HiDALGO2 CoE (website, social media channels, etc.), managing rotation plans for production of content, and maintaining up-to-date databases of publications produced by HiDALGO2, collaborations, and event participations. Future Needs is also leading the organisation of a Clustering Event planned for autumn 2025.

2.2 Communication activities

Communication activities focus on raising awareness of the HiDALGO2 project, its research, societal value, and results among a broad audience. For such efforts, the online channels maintained by the project form key outlets. D6.1 lays out in detail the

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strategy implemented by the HiDALGO2 project, with communication outputs including regular blog and social media posts and newsletters. These are reported on in detail in D6.2 and in sections 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 of this report.

In addition to the project KPIs reported in these sections, additional engagement metrics are continually monitored. These helps identify what types of content and formats resonate most with readers and drive organic reach through shares and likes on social media. Future Needs, which leads the relevant Task 6.5, draws on its specialist expertise and coordinates with partners to ensure that best practices are applied when creating and publishing content online. Practices such as tagging relevant parties in social media posts, publishing posts at times of peak engagement, ensuring images graphics are attractive and well-designed are implemented to ensure content receives broad attention.

Ensuring the format, content and presentation of the communication materials produced by HiDALGO2 are engaging and professional supports the broad goals of maximizing the impact of the project, building its reputation as a key CoE in the fields of HPC, AI and addressing Global Challenges and facilitating the widespread dissemination of project results, discussed below.

2.3 Dissemination activities

Dissemination activities focus on transferring knowledge and results to key target audiences. For the HiDALGO2 project, these include the research community, industry and policymakers.

Such activities include the publication of scientific papers as detailed in section 4.1, participating in conferences and other events, as described in section 5.1, and through collaborations and clustering activities, described in 5.2 and 5.3 respectively. These dissemination channels are amplified by the communications described in section 2.2 above, with social media and website posts highlighting partners’ past and upcoming activity. Posts advertising HiDALGO2 participation in an upcoming event, for example, can facilitate connection-building with other projects, research groups and stakeholders, increasing impact.

By April 2025, the HiDALGO2 project had attended over 30 different events, surpassing the relevant KPI for the project’s duration. A total of 12 scientific papers had been published in peer-reviewed journals.

Another key element of the HiDALGO2’s dissemination strategy is conducting trainings to “collect and share knowledge, best practices, available resources and mechanisms for appliances, applications and software frameworks for tackling the identified Global Challenges with HPC and AI” [5]. The HiDALGO2 project has conducted or participated in a total of 9 such training events [5]. Such trainings are also promoted across the project’s communication channels. However, as these are reported on separately in

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D6.8 [6], D6.9 (due M29) and D6.10 (due M48), such trainings are not covered in additional detail in this report.

2.4 Synergies and clustering activities

HiDALGO2 actively engages in synergies and clustering efforts to maximise impact, foster collaboration, and enhance knowledge exchange across the HPC and AI ecosystem.

As described in section 5.2, building on the foundation established during the previous HiDALGO project, the consortium has strengthened relationships with several CoEs, national and European initiatives, and international projects. Notably, HiDALGO2 maintains a close collaboration with CASTIEL2 to promote competencies and services to users, and contributes technically to shared platforms and initiatives.

The project has co-organised and participated in multiple joint workshops, conferences, and hackathons with projects including SEAVEA, CIRCE, and NUMPEX, facilitating knowledge sharing. HiDALGO2 also engaged with the Horizon Results Booster service to explore exploitation strategies and joint dissemination with other CoEs.

A dedicated clustering event, scheduled for autumn 2025 and outlined in section 5.3, will further support outreach to industry, foster new collaborations and synergies, and showcase project results and partner contributions within the wider European HPC community.

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3 Online communication and dissemination platforms

3.1 Website

The dedicated website of the HiDALGO2 project [7] forms a central pillar of the project’s communication and dissemination efforts. Through the portal, visitors can find in-depth information about the HiDALGO2’s project’s focus, goals, expected outcomes, consortium and funding, and stay up-to-date on the latest developments through the course of the project.

3.1.1 Website traffic analysis

The targeted KPI for the website is to have 8,000 unique visitors [3] [4] by the end of the project (M48). At the end of M28 (April 2025), **4,582 unique visitors** had visited the website. For the relevant KPI to be achieved, the website will need to receive at least an average of approximately 175 unique visitors per month.

As can be seen in Figure 1 below, for the majority of months since November 2023, the website has received over 200 visitors each month, falling below this level only in August and December of 2024, with the relatively lower levels of traffic during these months likely due to the holiday periods associated with these times of the year [8]. As such, it is considered that the HiDALGO2 website is **on track to achieve the KPI of 8,000 unique visitors by the end of the project.**

Figure 1. Monthly visitors to HiDALGO2 website (Aug 2023 - April 2025)

Further analysis of the website traffic provides additional insight on the performance of the HiDALGO2 website as a whole and its component sections.

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Table 1. Top referrers to HiDALGO2 website

Referrer	Unique Visitors	% Total Visitors
Direct	2556	51.43%
Google (Search)	1428	28.73%
LinkedIn (Social)	357	7.18%
X (Social)	85	1.71%

Table 1 above shows the top 5 sources of traffic to the HiDALGO2 website [8]. As can be seen, **direct entries** (i.e. where users access the site without being referred by social media or another online source for which data is collected) account for approximately half of all entries of unique visitors. This indicates that a significant proportion of users access the site via sources that do not pass referral information. While further detail is unavailable on the precise sources, these are likely to include project newsletters, emails, pdfs, presentations, instant messages, etc, both originating from the HiDALGO2 project and within the broader research community. Notably, this category of users is highly engaged with an **average visit duration of 9.53 min (compared to 3.29 min for those visitors entering via LinkedIn)** [8].

Significantly, traffic **via Google Search** is the second most important source of traffic for the website, indicating the HiDALGO2 website is readily discoverable via search engines in response to relevant queries. Meanwhile, traffic via links shared on **social media** accounts for approximately 10% of visitor entries, according to the data collected [8].

3.1.2 Static content

As described in D6.1 [1] and D6.2 [2], all content uploaded is provided by the consortium and managed and edited by the Dissemination Leader (FN). This content is uploaded in the correspondent sections, (as presented in Table 2 in D6.1) and can be divided into static content (e.g. the About section) and dynamic content (e.g. blog and news posts - discussed below).

Table 2 provides an overview of the top-performing pages to date [8]. As can be seen, 12 of the 15 top-performing pages fall into the category of static content, with this content accounting for approximately two-thirds of all page views. This indicates high levels of interest in the HiDALGO2 project as an undertaking, with a significant proportion of this traffic likely originating from queries on Google Search and other search engines.

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Table 2. Top performing pages on HiDALGO2 website (Aug 2023 - April 2025)

Rank	Page Title	Type of content	Views	% Total Views
1	Home	Static	4497	29.89%
2	News	Dynamic	1384	9.20%
3	About	Static	1382	9.19%
4	Consortium	Static	621	4.13%
5	Deliverables	Dynamic	549	3.65%
6	People	Static	503	3.34%
7	The Urban Air Project	Static	496	3.30%
8	Hackathon by HiDALGO2, CIRCE and SEAVEA projects – 5 to 7th of June 2024 (blog post) [9]	Dynamic	430	2.86%
9	Trainings	Dynamic	350	2.33%
10	Wildfires	Static	280	1.86%
11	Urban Building Model	Static	273	1.81%
12	Partners	Static	263	1.75%
13	Workshop on Advancements of Global Challenges Applications (AGCA)	Dynamic	217	1.44%
14	Material Transport in Water	Static	171	1.14%
15	Contact	Static	154	1.02%
N/A	All other blog/news posts	Dynamic	2595	17.25%

Significant levels of traffic are drawn by each of the **five Use Cases webpages** (Urban Air Project, Urban Building Model, Renewable Energy Sources, Wildfires, Material Transport in Water). Considering the pivotal role these Use Cases play in the HiDALGO2 project, these pages form a key element in the project’s dissemination and communication activities. Originally drafted at the outset of the project by the relevant consortium partners, these are currently in the process of being updated with additional specifics about the work undertaken to date and relevant codes.

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3.1.3 Dynamic content (Blog / News) posts

The regularly updated dynamic content of the HiDALGO2 website includes the content uploaded to the **News / Blog section** of the website. As described in D6.1 [1] and D6.2 [2], a blog publishing schedule based on a monthly rotation plan involving all consortium partners is implemented. As of writing, **24 blog posts** have been published, 16 of which during the period of M13 to M27, as laid out in Table 3.

In addition, 43 news items have been published on the HiDALGO2 website [11] (see Annex). The articles refer to events attended by the partners of the HiDALGO2 project, the publication of scientific papers, noteworthy results, upcoming trainings and other developments in the project. In total, this dynamic content (in addition to pages that host this content - e.g. News / Trainings) accounts for 36.3% of the views on the HiDALGO2 website [8]. Since the beginning of the project until M27, 1,619 unique visitors have opened blog/news content on the HiDALGO2 website, with this content amassing a total of 3,271 views (as some unique users have visited more than one item of dynamic content). This accounts for 21.2% of all views amassed across the HiDALGO2 website [8].

Besides steering the partners to contribute this content or collaborating with them to create and edit it for the website, Future Needs promotes this content via social media and the regular newsletters produced and sent to the subscriber list. As described in D6.2 [2], the newsletters are available on the website via a dedicated section (these are discussed in section 3.2 below) [10].

Table 3. Blog posts on HiDALGO2 website published from M13 to M27

Blog No.	Release Month	Title	Contributor
10	M13 (January 2024)	“Women In Science” Campaign Angeliki Dimitriou [12]	FN, ICCS
11	M14 (February 2024)	The insights of HiPEAC Conference [13]	PSNC
12	M14 (February 2024)	“Women In Science” Campaign Ioanna Tasou [14]	FN, ICCS
13	M14 (February 2024)	Women In HPC Science [15]	FN, ICCS
14	M14 (February 2024)	“Women In Science” Campaign Vasiliki Kostoula [16]	FN, ICCS
15	M15 (March 2024)	Find out the basics of the HiDALGO2 Project [17]	FN

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Blog No.	Release Month	Title	Contributor
16	M16 (April 2024)	Pitch session at the 4th Baltic HPC and Cloud Conference [18]	HLRS
17	M17 (May 2024)	Assessing Computational Fluid Dynamics on GPU Using Portable Languages [19]	ATOS
18	M17 (May 2024)	HiDALGO2's Urban Building pilot: Updates and Roadmap [20]	UNISTRA/CEMOSIS
19	M19 (July 2024)	Particle-resolved simulation of antidunes in free-surface flows [21]	FAU
20	M19 (July 2024)	Advancements and Internships in Urban Building Energy Simulation [22]	UNISTRA/CEMOSIS
21	M19 (July 2024)	Diving into GPU Programming [23]	ATOS
22	M22 (October 2024)	Urban building modelling: enhancements in building geometry reconstruction [24]	UNISTRA/CEMOSIS
23	M22 (October 2024)	Generating Vegetation in Urban Areas for Energy Modeling [25]	UNISTRA/CEMOSIS
24	M24 (January 2025)	Scaling to new heights: Xyst code excites with unprecedented 196K core run on LUMI supercomputer [26]	FN, SZE

3.1.4 Scientific publications & deliverables

All published scientific articles and public deliverables have been published on the HiDALGO2 website where they are openly accessible to all visitors. The relevant links are [\[27\]](#) and [\[28\]](#), with each section readily accessible via the homepage via the top menu. Deliverables are accessible as a direct download from the HiDALGO2 website, while scientific publications are provided as links to open access journals or open access repositories (Zenodo) where the full text of the papers can be downloaded. In addition, all public deliverables and scientific publications are uploaded to the ResearchGate portal, rendering them easily discoverable and accessible to the research community active on the site. All public deliverables include "HiDALGO2" in the title and are thus easily found through the search function [\[29\]](#)

3.2 Newsletter

As described in D6.1 [\[1\]](#) and D6.2 [\[2\]](#), the HiDALGO2 newsletter is published three times per year. To date, six newsletters have been published. A schedule for the

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release of newsletters was laid out in D6.1, which was modified during the course of the project to align with project activities. The planned and actual release dates of the newsletter can be seen in Table 4 below.

In terms of readership, the targeted KPI for the newsletter is to reach 300 individuals/organisations signed up to receive the newsletter by M48, with 150 signed up at the mid-point of the project (M24) [3], [4]. However, as of M24, fewer than 130 subscribers had registered to receive the newsletter via email, with the growth trend remaining below the level needed to achieve the targeted KPI. With the aim of making the newsletter more readily available to users outside of the HiDALGO2 website, and drawing on experience from other EU-funded projects, Dissemination leader Future Needs proposed moving the newsletter to LinkedIn, with consortium members agreeing to the proposal.

While this change entailed the disadvantage of requiring existing subscribers to re-subscribe to the HiDALGO2 newsletter on LinkedIn to continue to receive updates, the high level of engagement among the existing subscriber list indicated that a high proportion of the existing subscribers would take the action required and re-subscribe. Compensating for this drawback associated with the change, the move to LinkedIn was expected to facilitate new subscribers by making the newsletter more readily available to the social media platform’s large user base among the relevant research, scientific and academic community, as well as the HiDALGO2 project’s own followers on the platform, the majority of whom had not subscribed to the newsletter.

Figure 2. Screenshot of the HiDALGO2 Newsletter #6 on LinkedIn

the number of subscribers surpassing that of the existing email list within 2 days, and as of writing standing at 191 followers [31]. Additional strategies are planned to increase the number of subscribers, such as use of social media campaigns and promotion of the newsletter during event and conference attendance through QR codes, ensuring that the KPI of total subscribers will be attained. Note that the original

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email list of 130 subscribers has not been counted in the KPI progress during reporting, although not all contacts overlap.

As laid out in D6.1 [1] and D6.2 [2], all published newsletters are available in the News section of the HiDALGO2 website [32]. Earlier versions of the newsletter are available as downloadable pdfs, while the corresponding link for Newsletter 6 directs users to the newsletter on LinkedIn [30]. The latter will be the case for all subsequent newsletters presented in the table below.

Table 4. Newsletter publications plan M13-M48

Newsletter Issue	Month Published / Scheduled
3 rd	M14 (February 2024) [33]
4 th	M17 (May 2024) [34]
5 th	M22 (November 2024) [35]
6 th	M25 (January 2025) [30]
7 th	Scheduled M29 (May 2025)
8 th	Scheduled M33 (September 2025)
9 th	Scheduled M36 (December 2025)
10 th	Scheduled M40 (April 2026)
11 th	Scheduled M45 (September 2026)
12 th	Scheduled M48 (December 2026)

3.3 Social media

Social media networks are a vital element in the HiDALGO2 project’s dissemination and communication activities, comprising a key avenue for the broader scientific and academic community, as well as the general public, to discover the project and be informed of project news such as the publications of scientific articles, partners’ participation in events, HiDALGO2 training events and more. Further, social media networks greatly facilitate the formation and strengthening of connections between the HiDALGO2 project and its consortium partners with the broader HPC community.

The HiDALGO2 project maintains an active presence on social media via its dedicated accounts on key networks. including LinkedIn [36], X (formerly Twitter) [37], Facebook [38] and YouTube [39]. In January of 2025, largely in response to shifts in the social media landscape driven by broader geopolitical developments, an account was also created on BlueSky [40] (discussed in sections 3.3.2 and 3.3.3 below). However, LinkedIn is by far the most effective platform for the project’s dissemination and

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communication, with a significantly larger audience of followers than any of the other platforms used by the project and higher rates of engagement.

With regard to the relevant KPIs, these have already been exceeded or are on track to be met. More specifically, KPIs of total number of likes on social media and number of followers on X have been already achieved. For LinkedIn, the KPI of followers is expected to be met well in advance of M48 (see table X in the Annex and dedicated sections).

The strategy for social media as outlined in D6.1 [1] and updated through D6.2 [2], remains the key tool defining the role of all partners and their contribution.

3.3.1 LinkedIn

Figure 3. A screenshot of the HiDALGO2 profile page on LinkedIn

As mentioned above, LinkedIn accounts for the majority of engagement by users on social media with content produced by the project. The relevant **KPI for LinkedIn is 750 followers** by the end of the project (M48) [4]. As of writing, the HiDALGO2 project’s following on LinkedIn stands at **521 followers** [36], with continuous growth over the course of the past year (see Figure 3). The period April 15, 2024 - April 15, 2025 saw a net gain of 191 followers, which corresponds to an **average gain of 15.9 followers per month**. Assuming this average rate of growth continues, the project is on track to exceed the relevant KPI by M48.

It should also be noted that periods of higher follower growth tend to coincide with public events in which the HiDALGO2 project is present, highlighting the impact of participation in events on metrics such as social media engagement. For example,

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relatively high levels of follower growth were seen during the months of May and June 2024, a period when the HiDALGO2 project participated in several events including the ISC High Performance 2024 event in Hamburg, Germany, and held its annual plenary meeting.

Figure 4. Cumulative growth of HiDALGO2 followers on LinkedIn

Additionally, the examination of the follower list on the platform confirms that a high proportion are professionals active in HPC or other fields related to areas of focus for the HiDALGO2 project.

In terms of content, over the past 12 months, (April 2024 - April 2025), a total of 138 posts/reposts were published on the HiDALGO2 LinkedIn page, garnering 36,800 impressions (the number of times the post appeared on individuals’ news feeds) and 1059 likes (the number of times users clicked one of the six reaction buttons that LinkedIn displays on every post). Two examples of top performing posts are provided below. These combine elements of best practice widely accepted to promote engagement such as tagging specific individuals and organisations involved, incorporating attractive visual elements, and being easily understandable and self-contained.

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Figure 5. Two of the top performing posts on LinkedIn over the period 15/4/2024 - 15/4/2025

3.3.2 X (Formerly Twitter)

X is the second most important platform for the HiDALGO2 project in terms of follower count and engagement, although these (and particularly the latter) are significantly below the comparable measures for LinkedIn. As of April 2025, the follower count for the HiDALGO2 project account stands at 460. While this is marginally higher than the follower count reported in D6.2 of 434 (referring to December 2023), and exceeds the KPI of 300 followers by M48, this marks a decline from previous highs, having reached 475 in September of 2024. Current trends in follower growth appear to be stable or slightly negative.

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Figure 6. Screenshot of the HiDALGO2 profile page on X.com

The precise reasons for this decline are unclear, although this is not isolated to the HiDALGO2 project, with other EU-funded projects having reported similar outcomes [41]. Given that the drop in HiDALGO2’s follower numbers has largely coincided with international political developments related to the platform and its owner, it is believed that individuals opting out of the platform of their own volition is a significant factor for this drop of followers. This would align with broader developments that have been widely reported regarding X, with large numbers of members of the scientific and research community, including major European institutions [42] abandoning the platform for other alternatives, with the Bluesky platform emerging as a favourite [43]. Recent analysis by Altmetric for example, found that while X continues to have a far greater volume of overall posts than Bluesky, in the month of March 2025, on most days, Bluesky hosted more posts linked to new research than X [44].

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Figure 7. Screenshot of the HiDALGO2 profile page on Bluesky

Given the trends described above in section 3.3.2 regarding X, and to ensure the HiDALGO2 project is active on the platforms on which the HPC research community is active, following consultation with the consortium partners during regular meetings, a decision was made to launch an account for the HiDALGO2 project on Bluesky [40]. This follows a similar move by other relevant institutions such as the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking and multiple NCCs.

The HiDALGO2 Bluesky account was created in January 2025 with this communicated to all consortium members and to the recipients of the HiDALGO2 newsletter, along with the invitation to follow the account. The account currently has 22 followers, and it is expected that future gains on this platform will offset potential future losses of followers on X.

Moving forward, the HiDALGO2 project will post the same original content on Bluesky as is posted on X, according to the plan laid out in D6.1 [1]. As Dissemination leader, Future Needs will also regularly repost content deemed valuable to HiDALGO2’s followers and engage in other activities and campaigns to further grow the project’s following and engage in community building on the platform. monitoring analytics and adapting strategy to make the most effective use of the platform that appears to be becoming an important alternative to X, particularly among the research community [43].

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3.3.3 Facebook

Figure 8. Screenshot of the HiDALGO2 profile page on Facebook

While not foreseen in the project Grant Agreement, HiDALGO2 also has a Facebook page [38] through which it has shared similar content as that posted on LinkedIn and X. However, here impact has been limited, with the project amassing only 66 followers as of April 2025 (M28), with only 13 new followers added after M12, many of whom also follow the project on LinkedIn and X.

Due to low levels of engagement, the decision was made to reduce posting frequency on the platform, replacing the top post with a pinned post directing users to the project’s LinkedIn page.

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3.3.4 YouTube

Figure 9. Screenshot of the HiDALGO2 profile page on Youtube

While not foreseen in the project Grant Agreement, the HiDALGO2 project maintains a dedicated YouTube channel [39] to disseminate video content and enhance outreach to relevant stakeholders. All videos uploaded to the channel are also promoted through the project’s website and social media platforms to maximize visibility. As of writing the channel has **31 subscribers** [39].

To date, **13 videos** have been published by the HiDALGO2 project, amassing a total of **745 views** [39] (the channel also features an additional 22 videos “inherited” from the predecessor HiDALGO project). As the project progresses, relevant video content created, such as from trainings and simulations, will be posted on the YouTube channel, with these videos promoted on social media and embedded in blog and news items. Posting this content on YouTube will further facilitate discovery of the project by interested users conducting relevant searches within YouTube as well as external search engines.

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3.4 Partners websites

Partners in the HiDALGO2 project support the project’s visibility by featuring it on their institutional websites and within their national and international networks. These partner pages serve as additional platforms for audiences to discover the project, learn about its aims, and access the main HiDALGO2 website. Partners also share references to the project and developments in their relevant work through their own social media accounts. Below is a list of HiDALGO2 pages hosted by consortium members:

Table 5. Partners’ Websites with Information about HiDALGO2

Partner	Country
Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC) [45]	Poland
High-Performance Computing Center Stuttgart (HLRS) [46]	Germany
Meteogrid SL (MTG) [47]	Spain
FutureNeeds (FN) [48]	Cyprus

3.5 Communication on other platforms

3.5.1 GitHub

Figure 10. Screenshot of the HiDALGO2 discussions on the GitHub page of the Feel++ Consortium

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GitHub serves as an additional platform for partners in the HiDALGO2 project, facilitating the sharing of code, models, and technical discussions among consortium members and the broader research community.

Specifically, the Urban Buildings pilot application leverages GitHub to undertake collaborative work and disseminate relevant codes and results. The repository supports collaborative development, continuous integration workflows, and deployment on EuroHPC systems, helping to streamline the development process and ensure that contributions are well-managed.

The relevant discussions can be found at the profile page of the Feel++ Consortium (lead partner UNISTRA) [\[49\]](#) under the discussions with the label ":eu: Cemosis: CoE Hidalgo2" [\[50\]](#).

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4 Publications

As described in D6.1 “Brand and Roadmap for Awareness Campaign” [1], the HiDALGO2 project has committed to publishing a total number of **25 peer-reviewed articles and 10 popular science articles**, as the research conducted advances. The procedure of submission is detailed in D6.1.

4.1 Scientific publications

The publication of peer-reviewed papers forms a vital aspect of the dissemination strategy. During 2024 and until April 2025, 12 scientific papers have been accepted for publication. In accordance with the relevant Grant Agreement [3], “HiDALGO2 stands for open access by encouraging researchers to select the open access option for publications, unless there is not such an option in the conference/journal where the research will be published.” All but four of the scientific publications to date, namely [58], [59], [60], and [61] have been published via open access journals or are available on the open access repository Zenodo. As described in section 3.1.4, all scientific publications are also accessible to the research community via the portal ResearchGate.

Table 6. Scientific Publications

Date	Title	Partners
5 January 2024	Open-source complex-geometry 3D fluid dynamics for applications with unpredictable heterogeneous dynamic high-performance-computing loads. [51]	SZE
6 May 2023	Complex-Geometry 3D Computational Fluid Dynamics with Automatic Load Balancing. [52]	SZE - Joint with researchers of Los Alamos National Laboratory
15 May 2024	Using dispersion models at microscale to assess long-term air pollution in urban hot spots: A FAIRMODE joint intercomparison exercise for a case study in Antwerp. [53]	SZE - Joint with other FAIRMODE researchers
Sept 2024	Uncut-GEMMs: Communication-Aware Matrix Multiplication on Multi-GPU Nodes [54]	ICCS
29 Jul 2024	Structure Your Data: Towards Semantic Graph Counterfactuals [55]	ICCS
15 Dec 2024	Partition deactivation with load balancing for parallel flow simulations [56]	SZE
29 Sep 2024	AI for Global Challenges: Case Studies in Urban Solar Exposure and Wildfire Management [57]	ICCS

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Date	Title	Partners
1 April 2025	Efficient Allocation of Image Recognition and LLM Tasks on Multi-GPU System [58]	PSNC
1 April 2025	Simulation of Wildfires Using EuroHPC Resources: Challenges and Opportunities, David Caballero, Leydi Laura Salazar, Ángela Rivera, Luis Torres, [59]	MTG
1 April 2025	Ktirio Urban Building: A Computational Framework for City Energy Simulations Enhanced by CI/CD Innovations on EuroHPC Systems [60]	UNISTRA
1 April 2025	Fostering Uncertainty Quantification in Global Challenges with mUQSA Toolkit [61]	PSNC
1 March 2025	Prediction model of performance–energy trade-off for CFD codes on AMD-based cluster [62]	PSNC. SZE

4.2 Press and third party websites

By M48, HiDALGO2 aims for at least 10 articles highlighting the project and its results to be published in the press or on third-party websites. To date 4 such articles have been published which are presented in Table 4 or D6.2 [\[2\]](#). In the intervening period since the publication of that report, no additional press or third-party articles have been published.

As the research and the activities of the project advance further and more results are achieved, one or more additional press releases will be circulated among relevant outlets covering popular science, technology, HPC, AI and Global Challenges. As such, it is expected that this KPI will be met by the end of the project.

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5 Events, conferences and clustering activities

5.1 Events and conferences

A key and particularly fruitful element of the communication and dissemination strategy of the HiDALGO2 project, is the participation of the partners, as the project’s representatives, at a wide range of events, workshops and conferences related to HPC and addressing Global Challenges.

The relevant KPI, according to the D6.1 plan is attendance of 30 events over the duration of the project, which has already been achieved, with the HiDALGO2 project having been presented at 33 different events, workshops and conferences, listed in Table 7 below. (Note: the references to social media posts are available only for one year, due to policy of the platforms [\[86\]](#))

Table 7. Events attended by the HiDALGO2 Consortium

Event name	Date	Location	Participating partners
2024-01-29 & 30 Conference on Wildfires and Natural Risks (RIyRN) [63]	29-30 Jan, 2024	Spain	MTG
HIPEAC 2024 [64]	17 Jan 2024	Munich	PSNC, USTUTT, SZE
UME – Spanish Military Emergency Unit’s training [65]	Feb 2024	Spain	MTG
EuroHPC Summit 2024 [66]	18-21 Mar 2024	Antwerp, Belgium	PSNC
HPC Matching Day [67]	27 Mar 2024	Budapest	SZE
International Conference on Supercomputing (ICS) [68]	12-16 May 2024	Hamburg, Germany	FAU, USTUTT, PSNC
4th Baltic HPC and Cloud Conference [69]	11-12 Apr, 2024	Riga, Latvia	USTUTT
Scientific Computing Institute Association of Hungary’s event on HPC [70]	29 Apr 2024	Budapest	SZE
“Science Goes Society” event [71]	25 Apr 2024	Germany	USTUTT

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Event name	Date	Location	Participating partners
AIEnergyNN fairs [72]	23-24 Apr 2024	Poland	PSNC
National School of Civil Protection (Ministry of the Interior of Spain) - A course on operations and safety in urban-forest interface fires [73]	Apr 2024	Spain	MTG
CI/CD Framework for HPC Simulations in the context of the EuroHPC JU CI/CD activity coordinated by CASTIEL2 [74]	7 May 2024	Strasbourg, France	UNISTRA
Hackathon by HiDALGO2, CIRCE and SEAVEA projects [75]	5-7 Jun 2024	Stuttgart, Germany	USTUTT, METEOGRID, UNISTRA, PSNC, SZE
International Post-Exascale Workshop 2024 (InPEX) [76]	17-19 Jun 2024	Sitges, Spain	USTUTT, UNISTRA
ParCFD 2024 (the 35th International Conference on Parallel Computational Fluid Dynamics) on The mini-symposium about CI/CD and CFD (MS4: Modernizing CFD: Exploring CI/CD for Improved Software Development Life Cycle) got accepted [77]	2-4 Sep 2024	Bonn, Germany	USTUTT, FAU
AGCA event- 15th PPAM 2024 Conference (INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON PARALLEL PROCESSING AND APPLIED MATHEMATICS) [78]	8-11 Sep 2024	Ostrava, Czech Republic	PSNC
AI SyS 2024, focusing on HPC-AI convergence [79]	29 Sep - 4 Oct 2024	Venice	FAU

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Event name	Date	Location	Participating partners
International Conference for High-Performance Supercomputing (SC24) [80]	17-22 Nov 2024	Atlanta, US	USTUTT
1st International Congress on Wildfire Prevention [81]	3-4 Oct 2024	Argentina	MTG
“Becoming a zettabytes economy. Advanced data centres impact & what Beyond?” [82]	17 Oct 2024	Poznan, Poland	PSNC
VI Technical Conference on Wildfire Fighting [83]	22 Oct, 2024	Spain	MTG
EuroHPC Summit 2025 [84]	18-19 Mar 2025	Krakow, Poland	PSNC, USTUTT, SZE
High Performance Computing (#HPC) and Big Data Technologies for Global Challenges @ EuroCC Cyprus [85]	8 Apr 2025	Cyprus, Greece	FAU

5.2 Collaborations

HiDALGO2 is actively cooperating with other Centres of Excellence (CoEs) as happened previously in HIDALGO to develop better results and boost the outreach of the project. A relationship with CASTIEL2 has been established to promote project competencies and services to industrial users.

As detailed in D6.2, Chapter 6 “Collaborations and Synergies”, to maximise its impact, HiDALGO2 is involved in various actions, committed with collaboration agreements, which remain active [\[2\]](#).

Below find the collaboration actions from January 2024 until May 2025:

1. CI/CD Training together with Karolina, March 24th-26th 2025, online. Session title: "Containerization, CI/CD, and Benchmarking Solutions for HPC"
2. Collaboration with SEAVEA (UK project) and CIRCE (German project). In this collaboration, a UQ (Uncertainty Quantification) Hackathon was prepared and held on the 5 to 7 of June, 2024. Participants had the opportunity to define their own objectives, and to engage in hands-on learning interacting with experts on the SEAVEAtk (toolkit for UQ studies). They thus received tailored guidance on applying SEAVEAtk or mUQSA (software developed by the HiDALGO2 partner PSNC, based on SEAVEAtk) on their own codes and applications. Existing

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SEAVEAtk users also joined the hackathon, profiting from the support to add more rigorous VVUQ to their applications. The hackathon was open and free of charge for all participants.

3. Participation in the Horizon Booster Service (HRB). HRB is a free of charge service provided by the European Commission (<https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>) . USTUTT together with other partners from the Consortium was involved in the following activities: exploitation strategy, market access, IPR analysis, joint dissemination of a project group (together with the Plasma-PEPSC and EXCELLERAT P2 CoEs)
4. Contribution with the CASTIEL 2 Gitlab CI/CD platform. USTUTT was involved in the technical Working Group and the Proof-of-Concept activities in order to provide the technical support and expertise in the field of CI/CD technologies
5. Technical collaboration to the initiative led by CASTIEL 2 on GPU porting/code optimization (session attendance and identification of possible further collaboration on identified subtopics)

The stakeholders the consortium collaborated with were:

- CASTIEL2
- SIAM (Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics)
- EuroHPC
- SEAVEA (Software Environment for Actionable & VVUQ-evaluated Exascale Applications)
- CIRCE (Computational Immediate Response Centre for Emergencies)
- NUMPEX (Numeric for Exascale)
- EXCELLERAT P2
- Plasma-PEPSC

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5.3 HiDALGO2 Clustering Event

Figure 11. A screenshot of the announcement of the Clustering Event on the HiDALGO2 homepage

As part of its clustering activities, HiDALGO2 is organising a dedicated Clustering Event on 4th November 2025 at HLRS in Stuttgart, Germany [87]. Coordinated by Future Needs, this event will serve as a forum for collaboration and knowledge exchange among stakeholders in the HPC and Big Data domains. The event is aimed at researchers, industry professionals, policymakers and SMEs in the technology sector. The relevant KPI is for 60 attendees at the clustering event [3], [4].

As of April 2025, the agenda remains under development but will include expert-led discussions on HPC and Big Data applications, and training opportunities with contributions from a range of EU-funded projects funded under the European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking. The event will be promoted on the HiDALGO2 project channels, with a dedicated webpage about the event already live and a link prominently displayed on the HiDALGO2 homepage. It will be further promoted across other channels followed by the HPC community, such as the HPC in Europe portal being developed and operated as part of the CASTIEL2 project.

The event will be a primarily in-person event, with the facilities of HLRS selected due to their central location and good travel connections with other major European HPC research centres.

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6 Conclusions

Overall, the Dissemination and Communication activities of the HiDALGO2 project up until the end of April 2025 (M28) have achieved satisfactory results. Relevant KPIs are met, or on track to be met given continued implementation of the roadmap laid out in D6.1 together with the corrective actions identified in D6.2 and in this report.

More specifically, with regard to the project’s online communication, positive results have been observed in the online traffic to the project website, with the relevant KPI set to be met, given the continuation of existing trends in visitor numbers. Notably, a relatively high proportion of website visitors (roughly 1 in 3) enter the site via search engines. This indicates that SEO (search engine optimisation) best practices should continue to be implemented for future content as a priority to maintain and promote the project’s visibility to users who search for relevant queries. Direct entries (entries for which there is no referrer information) are also a major source of traffic for the HiDALGO2 website, indicating that traffic sources such as privately shared links (e.g. in emails or instant messaging applications), newsletters, presentations, etc. are important drivers of traffic to the website. This further reinforces the view that all aspects of the project’s communication and dissemination operate synergistically, and that efforts should be made to ensure that users can easily access more information about any given topic regardless of where they first come into contact with it. In practice this means ensuring that all materials produced by the project (e.g. emails, posters, training materials, etc.) have relevant website links and clear signposting to allow users to easily access additional resources.

Following a period of relative slow growth in the number of subscribers to the project’s newsletter, the corrective action was taken to transfer the newsletter from an email based mailing list to LinkedIn Newsletter. The months from January 2025 to April 2025, saw a period of rapid subscriber growth, supporting the case for this transition. Future efforts will be on the platform and elsewhere made to further ensure potential subscribers are aware of the new newsletter location as a means to stay informed of developments in the HiDALGO2 project.

With regard to social media, LinkedIn is and will likely remain the most important such channel for dissemination and communication of the project’s undertakings and results, having built an engaged following of users with specific interests in the fields of HPC, AI and addressing Global Challenges. Efforts in this space should focus on keeping this community engaged and continuing to grow the following in order to meet the relevant KPI by the end of the project. Communication on this channel will also aim to support activities in all other tasks under WP6, such as the organising and hosting of training sessions, promoting the Clustering Event being organised, and facilitating and deepening collaborations. This will be further supported by active communication on other platforms, including X (formerly Twitter) and Bluesky, to ensure the

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HiDALGO2 project is an active participant on platforms where the relevant research communities and stakeholders are active.

Dissemination of technical advances and other results from the project through the publication of scientific papers is proceeding satisfactorily, with 12 papers published by M28 of the project, accessible via the HiDALGO2 website. In order for the KPI of 25 peer-reviewed publications by M48 to be achieved, continued efforts are required in this area by all consortium partners. As additional results are expected to emerge from the ongoing research from M28 until M48 of the project, it is expected that this KPI will be met. As leader of WP6, Future Needs will coordinate relevant activity by consortium partners during the monthly WP6 meetings, ensuring a viable strategy to achieving the required number of papers is in place. The publication of additional scientific results will also support the publication of at least one additional press release by the end of the project as foreseen by the Grant Agreement [3], and additional popular articles on third-party websites presenting key findings, technologies and applications developed for a broad audience.

In terms of event/conference participation and collaborations, the HiDALGO2 consortium has been highly active, indicating that the initial strategy laid out in D6.1 is viable and being implemented. Key focuses in this area will be continuing and deepening existing partnerships and forging new collaborations and synergies, such as through the updated HPC in Europe Portal currently being developed through the CASTIEL2 project with which HiDALGO2 has an ongoing collaboration. This will also support broad participation in the Clustering Event being organised in November 2025 which will form a key element of the project’s dissemination and communication strategy in the intervening months.

Overall, the positive momentum demonstrated across all communication and dissemination channels provides a strong foundation for reaching the remaining targets through to project completion, and ensuring the impacts of the HiDALGO2 project are maximised.

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Annex

Table 8. News/Event posts on HiDALGO2 website

No.	Publication Date	Title
1	13/02/2023	HiDALGO2 in CASTIEL2 Kick-offEdit
2	24/02/2023	HiDALGO2 in SIAM CSE (CSE23)
3	01/04/2023	EuroHPC Summit 2023
4	06/06/2023	HiDALGO2 in ISC 2023
5	21/06/2023	Athens plenary meeting of the HiDALGO2 partners
6	12/10/2023	EuroHPC in Supercomputing Conference (SC23)
7	23/10/2023	HiDALGO2 in ICIAM 2023, Japan, August 2023
8	31/10/2023	HiDALGO Scientific Papers
9	09/11/2023	Joint Workshop HiDALGO in HiPEAC
10	20/11/2023	A Workshop Uncertainty Quantification by HiDALGO2, SEAVEA, and CIRCE
11	22/11/2023	EuroHyPerCon workshop on HPC connectivity needs
12	27/11/2023	Challenges and bottlenecks of our Urban Building pilot at NumPEX workshop on Discretization @Exascale
13	04/12/2023	Unlocking the sessions of the joint workshop on digital twins (HiDALGO2 & ESIWACE3 – HiPEAC Conference 2024)
14	06/12/2023	Insights of SC23 in Denver
15	06/12/2023	Collaborative Synergy: Highlights from the 3rd HiDALGO2 Partners Meeting
16	18/12/2023	HiDALGO2 in Big Data Value Association’s Task Force meeting
17	18/01/2024	WORKSHOP ON ADVANCEMENTS OF GLOBAL CHALLENGES APPLICATIONS (AGCA)
18	16/02/2024	The insights of HiPEAC Conference
19	19/02/2024	Hidalgo2 in Sevilla RIyRN
20	27/02/2024	HiDALGO2’s wildfire simulations presented at UME – Spanish Military Emergency Unit’s training
21	07/03/2024	HiDALGO2 at EuroHPC Summit 2024 Conference
22	20/03/2024	An overview of EuroHPC Summit 2024

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No.	Publication Date	Title
23	22/03/2024	“CoE HiDALGO2: Urban Building Modeling and Simulation” lecture
24	11/04/2024	Call for papers! Workshop on advancements of global challenges applications PPAM 2024 Conference
25	12/04/2024	Pitch session at the 4th Baltic HPC and Cloud Conference
26	15/04/2024	HiDALGO2 participates in ISC High Performance 2024
27	16/04/2024	Fire-atmosphere simulations of HiDALGO2 in the hands of civil protection
28	18/04/2024	Hackathon by HiDALGO2, CIRCE and SEAVEA projects – 5 to 7th of June 2024
29	25/04/2024	A CI/CD Framework for HPC Simulations 7 May 2024, University of Strasbourg
30	25/04/2024	HiDALGO2 at #AI EnergINN 2024
31	30/04/2024	Science Goes Society
32	10/05/2024	Hungarian HPC users gain valuable insights into the applications of HiDALGO2
33	13/05/2024	Three scientific papers by Széchenyi István University (SZE)
34	29/05/2024	Exploring HiDALGO2 at ISC High Performance 2024
35	21/06/2024	HiDALGO2 partners catching up in their 3rd plenary meeting in Stuttgart
36	25/06/2024	What we gained from the 2024 InPEX project’s workshop
37	09/07/2024	Uncertainty Quantification hackathon gets the attention of users
38	17/07/2024	Register now open! Workshop on Advancements of Global Challenges Applications 15th PPAM 2024 Conference
39	21/10/2024	HiDALGO2 on the International Congress on Wildfire Prevention
40	25/10/2024	Coordinator of HiDALGO2 in the event: ‘Becoming a zettabytes. The impact of advanced data centres and what lies Beyond’
41	01/11/2024	HiDALGO2 in the VI Technical Conference on Wildfire Fighting
42	19/12/2024	HiDALGO2 innovations in wildfire simulation captivate at SC24
43	11/02/2025	Training Session: Containerization, CI/CD, and Benchmarking Solutions for HPC

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Reference:	D6.3	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0
				Status:	Final

Table 9. KPIs Report Table

KPI Title	KPI measure	Goal	Achieved
Website	# of unique visitors	8000	666
Website	# of unique visitors	8000	4582
Press Releases	# of press releases	2	1
Newsletters	# of subscribers	150 / 300	191
	# of newsletters	12	6
Project Factsheet	# of downloads	250	154
	# of sheets distributed	750	100
Presentations at third party events	# of events attended	30	33
Peer-reviewed papers & popular science articles	# of publications of articles	25	8
	# of blog posts	46	24
	# of articles in 3rd party websites	10	4
Social Media	# of LinkedIn followers	750	521
	# of Twitter followers	300	460
	# of likes in Twitter & LinkedIn	2500	2947
HiDALGO2 Workshops & Clustering Event	#of stakeholders in the advisory board	15	5
	# of stakeholders engaged in project activities	10	6
	# of attendees of the clustering event	60	N/A